

Demographics Questionnaire -

- 1) Age: How old are you?
 - a) Please enter your age [free response]
- 2) Gender: What is your gender(identify with)?
 - a) Woman
 - b) Man
 - c) Non-binary
 - d) Describe yourself [free response]
 - e) Prefer not to answer
- 3) State: In which state do you live?
 - a) Please enter the state you live in [free response]
- 4) Education: What is your highest level of education?
 - a) No school leaving certificate
 - b) High school or equivalent leaving certificate
 - c) Diploma certificate
 - d) Bachelor's degree
 - e) Master's degree
 - f) PhD/doctorate
 - g) Prefer not to answer
- 5) Profession: What is your current employment status?
 - a) Employed full-time
 - b) Employed part-time
 - c) Self-employed/Freelancer
 - d) Independent contractor, freelancer, or self-employed
 - e) Not working
 - f) Not working (retired)
 - g) Prefer not to disclose
 - h) Prefer to self-describe [free response]
- 6) Income: What is your income range per year?
 - a) Upto 3 lakhs
 - b) 3 - 6 lakhs
 - c) 6 - 9 lakhs
 - d) 9 - 12 lakhs
 - e) 12 - 15 lakhs
 - f) Above 15 lakhs
 - g) Not Applicable
 - h) Prefer not to answer
- 7) Duration: How long have you been using UPI apps?
 - a) Less than 1 year
 - b) 1 - 2 years
 - c) 2 - 5 years
 - d) More than 5 years
- 8) UPI Apps: Which UPI apps do you use?
 - a) Please enter the UPI app names [free response]